

Kinetics and Mechanism of Acid-Hydrolysis of Benzhydrazide

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The kinetics of the hydrolysis of benzhydrazide in aqueous hydrochloric acid over the range 1 to 10 M, have been investigated spectrophotometrically at 90°. The reaction has been found to follow a pseudo-first order rate law. The reaction leads to the formation of cleavage products. The activation parameters have been evaluated. A mechanism in which the first step is the rapid and reversible formation of a protonated substrate followed by the attack of water molecule in the rate determining step has been suggested.

It has been found that hydrazides are generally stable to acids and bases in cold¹. They undergo hydrolytic cleavage to form free carboxylic acid in acidic medium only when the latter is strong². The hydrolysis of the hydrazides is likely to proceed by a mechanism similar to that of the hydrolysis of amides but no detailed studies have yet been reported on the kinetics and on the mechanism of the cleavage.

In this paper are described the studies of the kinetics and the mechanism of the acid-catalysed hydrolysis of benzhydrazide in an attempt to see its similarity with the amide hydrolysis³.

Experimental

Materials: Benzhydrazide prepared by a known method⁴, was recrystallized from water, m.p. 112.5°. Hydrochloric acid was used as a source of hydrogen ions. Sodium chloride was used to adjust the ionic strength. All other chemicals used were analytical grade reagents.

Kinetics: All kinetic experiments were carried out in a thermostat whose temperature was controlled to $\pm 0.05^\circ$. Reaction rates were determined spectrophotometrically using a Bausch and Lomb model Spectronic-20. Reaction solutions were prepared by pipetting the desired volume of a dilute solution (usually 2.344×10^{-4} M unless otherwise specified) of the benzhydrazide into a previously thermoequilibrated 100 ml. volumetric flask containing the desired volume of the hydrochloric acid, salt solutions for constant ionic strength runs and distilled water. The volume of the total reaction mixture was 50 ml. The rate constants were measured from the appearance of hydrazine⁵. At regular time intervals 2 ml. aliquots were transferred and quenched into a 25 ml. measuring flask containing the calculated amount of the reagent, *p*-dimethyl-amino-benzaldehyde. The required amount of the hydrochloric acid and water were then added to maintain 0.7 M acidity of the final solution. The optical densities were measured at 460 nm on spectronic-20 after 15 min.

Results and Discussions

Pseudo-first order rate constants in the hydrazide are independent of its change in concentration. The rate constants were found to increase with the increase in acid concentration upto 10 M acid. The rate never reaches maximum in the case of hydrazides probably on account of their less basicity when compared to amides. The first order kinetics was also observed in case of Acethydrazide⁶. As has been done for the acid hydrolysis of dimethyl phosphate⁷ and acetamide⁸, the rate constants were determined at the various acidities by keeping constant ionic strength and the results show that the rate of hydrolysis increases steadily with increase in stoichiometric acid concentration. From the plot of the rate coefficients against acidity at the different ionic strengths, it can be concluded that

- i) At each ionic strength the reaction can be represented by—

$$k = k_{H^+} C_{H^+} \quad \dots (1)$$

where k and k_{H^+} are the observed and specific rate constants.

- ii) Since the slopes (k_{H^+}) of the lines increase with increase in ionic strength, the reaction exhibits a positive ionic strength effect.
- iii) The reaction due to neutral species is absent as the lines of the graph pass through the origin⁸.

These results are in favour of the reaction via only protonated species which is subject to positive salt effect. The rate data in acid medium (Table 1) obey eqn. (2).

$$k = 18.41 \times 10^{-4} C_{H^+} e^{0.0615\mu} \quad \dots (2)$$

which is a modified form of Bronsted-Bjerrum equation applied to the conventional reaction scheme⁹.

where S is a hydrazide and $(X^\ddagger)$ is the transition complex.

The values, 18.41×10^{-4} litre mole $^{-1}$ min $^{-1}$ and 0.0615μ in eqn. (2) are respectively, the intercepts at the zero ionic strength ($k_{H_0^+}$) and the slope of the linear plot between $\log k_H^+$ and μ .

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF OBSERVED AND CALCULATED RATES FOR THE HYDROCHLORIC ACID CATALYSED HYDROLYSIS OF BENZHYDRAZIDE AT 90°

HCl	Calculated $k \times 10^3$ (min. $^{-1}$) eqn. 2.	Observed $k \times 10^3$ (min. $^{-1}$)		$3 + \log k$
1.0	1.96	1.54	2.309*	0.186
2.0	4.16	3.39		0.580
3.0	6.64	6.49		0.812
4.0	9.42	9.45		0.973
5.0	12.51	12.52	19.26*	1.082
6.0	15.97	17.01		1.231
7.0	19.81	21.94		1.341
8.0	24.08	25.13		1.400
9.0	28.80	30.27		1.481
10.0	34.04	33.79		1.519

* These rates are observed when D₂O is used in place of H₂O.

The values of Bunnett and Olsen¹⁰ parameter ($\phi = 1.33$) and hydration parameter¹¹ ($r = 3.4$) respectively, obtained from the plots of $(\log k + \text{Ha})$ Vs. $(\text{Ha} + \log H^+)$ and $(\log k + \text{Ha})$ Vs. $(\log a_{H_2O})$ ¹² indicate that water molecules should act as nucleophile and proton transfer agent in the rate limiting step.

The reaction is a specific acid catalysed reaction involving prior equilibrium formation of the conjugate acid of the substrate similar to amides¹³ as indicated by the rate ratio :

$$\frac{k_{D_2O}}{k_{H_2O}} = 1.5 \text{ (Table I)}$$

The probable reaction path consistent with the experimental data may be formulated as under :

The activation parameters of benzhydrazide were determined by measuring the rate of hydrolysis at 1 M HCl over a 15° temperature range.

Values of the activation parameters E (20.4 k.cals/mole), A (3.7×10^9 min $^{-1}$) and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ (-29.2 e.u.) are in favour of the proposed bimolecular mechanism. The errors limited in the values of log A, E and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ are ± 0.6 , ± 1.0 k.cal/mole and ± 2.0 e.u. respectively.

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